

MULTIFUNCTIONAL HEMOSORBENT BASED ON NATURAL SILK "BOMBYX MORI" FIBERS AND ITS PROPERTIES

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Abstract. *The given article presents the results of medical and biological studies of a fibrous multifunctional hemosorbent obtained through high-temperature hydrolysis under high pressure followed by repeated hydrolysis under the influence of physical factors (ultrasonic dispersion and microwave irradiation) of pure fibroin isolated from natural silk. Medical and biological studies of the multifunctional fibrous hemosorbent made from fibroin of natural silk include experimental research on the adsorption and absorption characteristics in blood and blood serum in model animals. A comparative analysis of the sorption parameters of the multifunctional hemosorbent derived from natural silk fibroin with hemosorbents widely used in medical practice has been conducted.*

Keywords: *Hemosorbent; fibroin; sorption activity; sorbents.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that at present time the development of highly effective technologies for the comprehensive processing of production waste is relevant, enabling the most complete use of raw materials in the production of hemosorbents while avoiding the accumulation and release of harmful substances into the environment. Fibrous waste from cocoons, produced in cocoon-processing enterprises, is a promising raw material for the production of hemosorbents. One of the methods addressing the issue of negative environmental impact is the development of various materials based on production waste. Materials created from waste are used in medicine, pharmaceuticals, and the chemical industry. This work presents several studies by the authors who have achieved positive results in obtaining sorbents. For example, Turkish scientists developed a technology for processing rice husks and obtained various sorbents. [1] The Japanese company Asahi Kasei Medical has produced a wide range of synthetic sorbents for plasmapheresis: Plasorba BR, Immusorba, Adacolumn, etc. [2] "Plasorba BR-350," a synthetic plasmasorbent based on styrene-divinylbenzene copolymer; "Adacolumn" – a plasmasorbent based on cellulose; "Immunosorba PH-350" – a plasmasorbent based on agarose. Russian scientists developed activated carbons of grades IGI (GSU), such as IGI – activated carbon developed by the Institute of Fossil Fuels specifically for medical purposes, which is a sorbent obtained from fossil coals. [3]

Definitely, the obtained activated carbons have a stable porous structure throughout the volume of the granule. The disadvantages of sorbents of this type are relatively high ash content and the release of sodium, potassium, calcium ions, etc., into the blood. [4]. Also, highly selective molecularly imprinted polymer sorbents synthesized from Pickering emulsions have become widely used.

In the work [5], microspheres of poly(methacrylic acid) were synthesized, imprinted with bisphenol. The only stabilizer used in the synthesis was silica particles. The obtained microspheres had a regular spherical structure and hydrophilic surfaces. The polymers showed excellent recognition ability for bisphenol A in repeated and competitive binding experiments.

According to literature, methods of apheresis therapy are used to treat hypercholesterolemia, where selective removal of cholesterol and lipoproteins from the patient's blood plasma is performed using plasmasorption with the use of immunosorbents as chromatographic carriers: a series of adsorbents produced in Russia by the company "POKARD". However, immunoaffinity sorbents have several disadvantages, such as limited shelf life, high complexity, and cost of production. The global market estimated the cost of producing monoclonal and polyclonal antibodies in 2024 at 150–200 billion dollars. [6]

Therefore, the creation of synthetic polymer sorbent materials with high selectivity for cholesterol (CH) may lead to a reduction in the cost of apheresis therapy procedures for treating patients with hypercholesterolemia (HCL) and thus improve the quality of life of the population. Despite the active search for synthetic alternatives to immunoaffinity sorbents, only a small number of modern studies focus on the creation of sorbent materials specifically for the selective extraction of CH and low-density lipoproteins (LDL) from blood plasma. However, despite numerous studies on the synthesis of molecularly imprinted polymers, the issue of creating molecularly imprinted polymers for the selective extraction of CH has not been addressed in current literature. At the same time, it has been established that surface non-covalent imprinting leads to the creation of polymers with easily accessible selective sorption centers and improved mass transfer of target molecules during sorption. Simultaneously, selective polymer sorbents synthesized as granules improve the binding of the target substance and enhance the hydrodynamics of the sorption column compared to sorbents made from irregularly shaped particles. According to literature data, particular interest among modern researchers is directed at the creation of polymer granules using Pickering emulsion polymerization, which enhances the environmental sustainability of the obtained polymer materials by using nanoparticles as stabilizers for polymer-monomer droplets.

Certainly, the combination of the advantages of Pickering emulsion polymerization and surface molecular imprinting opens up opportunities for creating sorbent materials with high selectivity towards the target component. Therefore, the creation of a new, original multifunctional hemosorbent based on non-toxic natural polymers is a relevant task for the fields of polymer chemistry, pharmacology, and medicine.

Additionally, hemosorbents represent a separate group of medical preparations and devices designed for blood and plasma detoxification and the treatment of a number of socially significant diseases. Based on the analysis of recent literature, it has been established that leading scientific centers worldwide are conducting research to create new, non-harmful hemosorbents based on derivatives of natural and synthetic polymers of both organic and inorganic origins. Hemosorption is also an effective method for removing toxic substances from the blood that are harmful to the

cells of the body. The procedure involves passing the blood flow through a cartridge filled with sorbent (a procedure known as hemoperfusion). [7]

What is more interesting, the first sorbents in earlier years were materials based on activated charcoal, capable of removing various toxic molecules-exotoxins (poisons), cytokines, pro-inflammatory mediators, bacterial products, as well as substances produced during cell breakdown. Their specificity and efficiency were limited, although they could remove a relatively large amount of toxic substances. In subsequent years, interest grew in developing more selective sorbents designed to selectively remove molecules of a specific structure, including toxic metabolites, without significantly affecting the vital components of the blood. The main principle behind creating such materials is the covalent immobilization of organic ligand molecules, which have high affinity for toxic molecules, on the surface of an inert carrier, thereby forming strong complexes with these molecules.

Currently, two main types of sorbents are used as a basis for developing medical-grade sorbents. The first type includes non-selective sorbents, with activated charcoal being a classical example. It is capable of adsorbing many organic compounds simultaneously. Depending on the pore structure, such materials exhibit sorption activity towards both "medium-sized molecules" (peptides with molecular masses from 500 to 5000 Da) and larger protein molecules, whose molecular masses can range from 10,000 to 50,000 Da. This type also includes a range of polymeric sorbents [8, 9]. The second type includes selective sorbents. These are synthetic materials with ligands immobilized on their surfaces, which have a high affinity for the molecule or complex they are designed to remove, including bacterial endotoxins—lipopolysaccharides [10, 11].

Moreover, the use of organic polymers as sorbents opens up vast possibilities for their chemical modification in order to impart selectivity and other required properties. For the first time, we have conducted research on the possibility of obtaining multifunctional sorbents from fibrous waste of natural silk. The tensile elongation of silk fibers is 19-22%. Silk waste is characterized by high elasticity and low elongation, which ensures that fabrics and products made from them are resistant to wrinkling during use. The density of silk waste is 1.42 g/cm³. In terms of hygroscopicity, silk waste occupies an intermediate position between cotton (8.5%) and wool waste (14-17%). At normal temperature and relative humidity, raw silk absorbs up to 11% moisture. The thermal stability of natural silk, unlike other natural fibers, is lower: when heated, silk fibers become stiff and brittle, so it is not recommended to heat them above 100°C; at 180°C, silk fibers are destroyed [12]. Currently, there are no pharmaceutical enterprises in the republic for the production of hemosorbents, and the needs of practical medicine are fully met through the import of hemosorbents.

Materials and Methods. The objects of the study were selected silk threads, defective *Bombyx mori* silkworm cocoons, and fibrous waste from silk processing at OOO "Khorezm Ipaghi." The main reagents used were supplied by SigmaAldrich: ethyl alcohol (96.0%, cat. No. 1.59010), benzene (99.9%, cat. No. 270790), vitamin B12 (98.0%, cat. No. V6629), HCl (37.0%, cat. No. H1758), LiCl (98.0%, cat. No. 203637), dimethylformamide (99.8%, cat. No. 227056), CaCl₂ (99.99%, cat. No. 499609), sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel (4–12%, 10 × 10 cm, cat. N. PCG2003); distilled water used was obtained using the DZ-10L11 distiller from Huanghua Faithful Instrument Co., LTD.

Through sequential treatment with benzene and a mixture of ethanol–distilled water, the fibrous waste and silk threads were purified three times from fatty-wax and inorganic impurities for 1 hour at a temperature of 50°C. The ethanol-to-distilled water ratio was 70:30 (vol%) respectively. The purity of the silk threads and fibrous waste was determined using the GOST 5556-2022 method, which resulted in a purity of 99.8%. To remove the water-soluble sericin from the structure of the silk threads, the obtained samples were treated with water at a temperature of 110°C and a pressure of 0.143 MPa for 24 hours [13]. The amino acid composition of sericin and silk fibroin was determined using the Agilent 6400 Series Triple Quadrupole LC/MS Systems (Shimadzu), following the method presented by A. Steven and D. Cohen [14].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. At present time research is being conducted at the Institute of Chemistry and Physics of Polymers, Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan (ICHP AS RUz), on the development of a third type of "multimodal" hemosorbents, which combine the properties of both selective and non-selective sorbents. The aim of these studies is to develop a method for separating sericin and fibroin from natural silk in an aqueous environment under high temperature and pressure conditions [15], which contributes to obtaining pure, water-soluble sericin without the need for additional purification, as well as a fiber-structured hemosorbent [16]. This is achieved by further hydrolyzing fibroin in an aqueous medium using superhigh-frequency radiation (microwave, MW) and ultrasonic dispersion (US). A fibrous, multifunctional hemosorbent was obtained under optimal conditions [17].

For assessing the sorption activity of the obtained product, studies were conducted to investigate the adsorption and absorption properties of the hemosorbent in human blood and plasma, as well as in experimental animals.

For this purpose, a special glass column with a diameter of 30 mm and a length of 350 mm was constructed, featuring a special filter to retain fine particles of the sorbent. Venous blood was drawn from the cubital vein of humans and from the ear vein of rabbits using a vacuum container with a piston, S-Monovette® with K3EDTA. The anticoagulant – potassium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) – was applied to the inner walls of the test tube in a liquid-fine dispersion form (the dilution is less than 1%); the amount of K3-EDTA added corresponds to a final concentration of 1.6 mg of EDTA per 1 ml of blood. The role of the anticoagulant is to bind calcium ions, thereby blocking the blood coagulation cascade. Blood cells (erythrocytes, leukocytes, and platelets) in the EDTA-stabilized whole blood sample remain stable for up to 24 hours.

However, immediately after blood collection, the vacuum tube with EDTA was thoroughly mixed by inverting it 8–10 times. Insufficient mixing may lead to platelet aggregation, the formation of microclots, or coagulation.

The hemosorbent was loaded into two-milliliter syringes and compacted to volumes ranging from 0.1 ml³ to 0.6 ml³. The resulting volumes of the hemosorbent were weighed, and using the formula

$$\rho = m * V \text{ (g/ml}^3\text{)}$$

where ρ is the density, V is the volume, and m is the mass, the density of the obtained hemosorbent membranes was calculated. A 3 ml solution of dyes -methylene blue and indigo carmine at

concentrations of 1 mg/ml, along with whole human blood and rabbit blood – was passed through the hemosorbent layer. For this purpose, the plungers and needles were removed from the syringes, and the syringes themselves were placed in test tubes, allowing the dyes and blood to pass through the hemosorbent membranes with different densities by gravity.

Table1.

Spectrophotometric assessment of the adsorption of dyes by hemosorbents of different densities

Volume of Hemosorbent, V, ml³	Mass of Hemosorbent, m, g	Density ρ (g/ml³)	Methylene Blue, Absorbance at 628 nm	Indigo Carmine, Absorbance at 410 nm
<i>Норма (до ГТ)</i>			2,824	2,778
0,1	0,08±0,01	0,02±0,001	2,817±0,22	2,732±0,70
0,2	0,16±0,01	0,03±0,001	2,801±0,20	2,720±0,74
0,3	0,31±0,02	0,09±0,01	2,435±0,83*	2,743±0,92
0,4	0,34±0,01	0,15±0,01	2,796±0,15	2,665±0,80
0,5	0,45±0,03	0,23±0,02	2,791±0,17	2,661±0,20

Note: Starting from a volume above 0.3 mL³, a press in the form of a syringe plunger was required to pass the solution through the membrane; compared to solutions up to the hemadsorbent *R≤0.002.

As seen in Table 1, the adsorption properties of the hemadsorbent increase proportionally with the density of the hemadsorbent packing in the carrier. However, with a packing density above 0.09-0.1 g/mL³, the pressure from the 3 mL liquid column is insufficient for the spontaneous passage of the solution through the hemadsorbent, so a press in the form of syringe plungers was used. Statistically significant adsorption was observed at a hemadsorbent density of 0.09-0.1 g/mL³.

The expanded blood parameters were determined from aliquots of whole human blood, with blood tests conducted on a hematological analyzer BC-3000 (Mindray, P.R. China) both before and after passing through the sorbent. Then, from blood aliquots (3 mL) passed through different volumes of hemadsorbent and from aliquots of blood not passed through the sorbent, serum was separated and studied for the presence of protein, lipid, and bilirubin fractions, as well as glucose and urea in a comparative aspect.

Besides that, the results of the studies showed that practically all volumes of hemadsorbent, to some extent, absorb the cellular elements of human whole blood (Table 2), as well as proteins, blood bilirubin, lipids, urea, and glucose (Table 3).

As shown in Table 2, the hemadsorbent volume of 0.2–0.6 cm³ statistically significantly (P≤0.0001) absorbs platelets, lymphocytes, leukocytes, basophils, and a mixture of monocytes and eosinophils. The absorption of erythrocytes is relatively low. The effect of the hemadsorbent on the amount of hemoglobin and hematocrit is insignificant.

According to the data presented in Table 3, absorption of total blood protein and albumin by all volumes of the hemadsorbent can be observed. It should be noted that the hemadsorbent with a volume of 0.2–0.3 cm³ absorbs protein and lipid fractions within the statistical error range. Additionally, when passing whole blood through hemadsorbent volumes greater than 300 μ L³,

syringe plungers had to be used to press the blood through the volumes of the hemadsorbent, whereas whole blood passed through hemadsorbent volumes of 0.1–0.3 mL³ by gravity. In this regard, serum from blood aliquots passed through hemadsorbent volumes greater than 0.3 mL³ showed hemolysis to some degree, and therefore, bilirubin fraction values in these sera cannot be considered. Statistically significant adsorption of urea and glucose was observed when using hemadsorbent with a volume of 0.3 mL³.

Thus, the hemadsorbent is most active as a sorbent in volumes of 0.2–0.3 mL³ with a density of 0.09–0.1 g/mL³.

Table2.

Human blood parameters before and after passing through different volume of hemadsorbent (n = 3, M ± m).

Volume of HH, V, mL ³	Leukocytes, 10 ⁹ /L	Absolute lymphocyte count, 10 ⁹ /L	Absolute count of the mixture of monocytes, basophils, and eosinophils, 10 ⁹ /L	Granulocyte count, 10 ⁹ /L	Hemoglobin, g/L	Erythrocytes, 10 ¹² /L RBC	Hematocrit, % HCT	Mean hemoglobin concentration in erythrocyte, g/L	Platelets in absolute numbers, 10 ⁹ /L	Thrombocrit, %
Norm (before HH)	5,97±0,02	1,40±0,04	0,2±0,04	4,53±0,06	123,67±0,56	4,16±0,02	36,97±0,06	334,0±1,10	215,33±1,48	0,263±2,14
0,1	1,63±0,09**	0,73±0,06*	0,17±0,05	0,77±0,06**	114,67±2,64	3,74±0,08	35,42±1,26	331,33±1,52	12,33±1,17**	0,015±0,001**
0,2	1,27±0,08**	0,80±0,04*	0,13±0,02	0,33±0,06**	115,33±1,17	3,80±0,05	35,93±0,27	315,0±1,67	12,0±0,37*	0,015±0,001**
0,3	0,27±0,02**	-	-	-	85,0±1,59*	2,83±0,02*	25,77±0,09*	322,0±2,76	9,33±0,92*	-
0,4	0,6±0,06*	0,55±0,02*	-	0,23±0,06**	94,3±1,48*	3,31±0,15	31,93±0,92	325,67±1,66	19,0±2,03*	0,02±0,001**
0,5	-	-	-	-	115,0±0,97	3,77±0,17	34,87±0,66	326,3±1,48	25,33±1,28**	0,035±0,001**
0,6	0,37±0,06**	-	-	-	111,33±0,92	3,95±0,02	35,73±0,44	321,67±5,5	12,0±1,1**	0,016±0,001**

Note: Compared to blood parameters in normal conditions without using hemadsorbent: *P<0.002, **P<0.0001

Table3.

Protein, lipid, and bilirubin fraction parameters of human blood before and after sorption through different volumes of hemadsorbent (n = 3, M ± m).

Volume of Hemosorbent, mL ³	TP	Alb	Chol	LDL	Trig	TBil	DBil	Glu	Urea
	g/dL (at 37°C)		mg/dL	mmol/L	μmol/L		mmol/L		
Norm (before hemosorbent)	60,40±0,61	31,57±0,52	344,83±1,79	0,89±0,01	1,37±0,06	39,33±0,60	21,55±0,18	2,62±0,15	243,35±6,98
0,1	54,97±1,53	25,13±0,40	250,07±2,72*	0,72±0,03	1,27±0,04	27,60±0,77*	16,91±0,66**	2,25±0,16	241,13±4,32
0,2	53,57±0,53	25,83±0,27	181,20±1,76**	0,73±0,02	1,26±0,03	24,33±0,84*	13,88±0,43**	2,07±0,06**	238,53±4,00
0,3	43,47±0,44*	24,47±0,58*	208,47±1,83*	0,72±0,01	1,12±0,02	Hemolysis	Hemolysis	2,01±0,10**	198,45±3,97*
0,4	53,07±0,66	24,50±0,22*	244,5±2,09*	0,52±0,02*	0,89±0,08*	Hemolysis	Hemolysis	1,90±0,08**	210,63±4,82*
0,5	46,97±0,88*	26,10±0,68	253,63±1,42*	0,66±0,03*	0,79±0,01*	Hemolysis	Hemolysis	2,13±0,15*	199,18±8,42*
0,6	45,03±0,66*	24,90±0,49*	183,50±2,31**	0,88±0,01	0,89±0,02*	Hemolysis	Hemolysis	1,73±0,12**	180,57±2,56**

Note: compared to blood serum indicators within the normal range without the use of hemosorbent: *P>0.05, **P≤0.05

Thus, the hemosorbent, as a sorbent, is most active in volumes of 0.2-0.3 ml³ with a density of 0.03-0.1 g/ml³; its volume and density should not exceed 0.2 ml³ and 0.03 g/ml³, respectively.

Adsorption and absorption of immunoglobulins of classes A and E. The adsorption and absorption properties of the hemosorbent were assessed based on the content of immunoglobulins (Ig A and E) in human blood before and after passing through different volumes of the hemosorbent

Table4.

Content of immunoglobulins of classes Ig A and E in human blood before and after sorption through different volumes of the hemosorbent (n = 6, M ± m).

Volume of hemosorbent, V, ml ³	Immunoglobulin A, g/l	Immunoglobulin E, IU/ml
Norm (before hemosorption)	31,3±2,06	215±6,43
0,1	30,6±1,87	136±4,31
0,2	20,4±1,51*	108±4,15*
0,3	18,6±1,33*	83±3,38*
0,4	12,5±1,26*	54±2,69*
0,5	8,3±0,97*	-
0,6	-	-

Note: compared to blood indicators within the normal range without the use of hemosorbent: *P<0.05

It was found that a hemosorbent volume of 0.1 ml³ insignificantly reduces the amount of Ig A by 1.02 times and Ig E by 0.63 times. Hemosorbent volumes in the range of 0.2–0.4 ml³ significantly reduce the concentration of immunoglobulins by 1.53 to 3.98 times. At a volume of 0.6 ml³, the hemosorbent adsorbs the studied immunoglobulin classes by 100%. Thus, the studied volumes of the hemosorbent (0.2–0.6 ml³) statistically significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) absorb immunoglobulins of classes A and E. The results of the research revealed the high adsorption capacity of the hemosorbent for immunoglobulins of classes A and E, allowing for its broad application in diseases with Ig E-dependent pathogenesis.

For evaluating the adsorption activity of the hemosorbent, it was designed a special glass column with a diameter of 30 mm and a length of 350 mm, equipped with a special filter to retain small particles. The columns filled with the sorbent were pre-washed with saline. After washing the column, filled with hemosorbent under optimal conditions, with isotonic solution and sterilization, it was presented to the laboratory of the State Unitary Enterprise of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center of Surgery named after V. Vakhidov, Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan. Based on the results of blood hemosorption in patients, it was determined that the obtained multifunctional hemosorbent based on silk fibroin is on par with the industrially produced carbon hemosorbent "Simplex-EC," produced in Russia.

The obtained hemosorbent based on silk fibroin was subjected to medical and biological testing. The results of the studies on the adsorption activity of the hemosorbent in human blood plasma purification are presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Determination of the adsorption activity of the hemosorbent in blood serum.

Blood Serum			
	Unit of Measurement	Before Adsorption	After Adsorption
Glucose	(mmol/l)	6,5	1,7
Urea	(mmol/l)	9,6	2,3
Creatinine	(μmol/l)	209	53
Amylase	(U)	70	18
Cholesterol	(mmol/l)	4,3	1,1
Total Protein	(g/l)	65	17,5
AST	(U)	80	23
ALT	(U)	88	25
Total Bilirubin	(μmol/l)	18	4,5

The adsorption properties of the hemosorbent based on fibroin, obtained by microwave (MW) irradiation followed by ultrasound dispersion, were compared with the well-known hemosorbent "Simplex-EC" (Russia). The results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6

Comparative Indicators of the Hemosorbent Obtained from Silk Fibroin and the Industrial Carbon Hemosorbent "Simplex-EC"

Type of Sorbent	Type of Sorbent		
	Creatinine	Vitamin B ₁₂	Bilirubin
Simplex-EC (Russia)	27,12	6,06	0,16
Hemosorbent Based on Fibroin (Uzbekistan)	78	6,6	4,05

As it can be seen from the table, the developed hemosorbent, obtained under optimal conditions based on hydrolyzed silk fibroin in an aqueous medium, has higher adsorption activity compared to the industrial carbon sorbent.

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CONCLUSION

By summarizing it should be suggested that the medico-biological properties of the fibrous, multifunctional hemosorbent, obtained based on fibroin through hydrothermal hydrolysis at high temperature and pressure in an aqueous medium, and additional hydrolysis under the influence of ultrasound dispersion and super-high-frequency radiation, were tested in model systems, blood, and blood sera of experimental animals. According to the results of the study, the obtained fibroin-based hemosorbent is a competitive medical product and is on par with foreign analogs based on activated carbon in terms of adsorption properties.

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